

A STUDY OF ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF PUPIL TEACHERS IN RELATION TO LOCUS OF CONTROL

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper was to examine the relationship between Locus of Control and academic achievement of male and female under B.Ed pupil teachers of Rohtak district. The study was conducted on a sample of 120 male and female of B.Ed pupil teachers, from B.Ed colleges of Rohtak district. Then adaptation of Hasnain and Joshi's Locus of Control scale was used to assess the locus of control of the pupil teachers. The result indicated that there was no significant positive correlation between external locus of control and academic achievement of the pupil teachers. Further it was found that male and female of B.Ed pupil teachers having internal Locus of Control help better academic achievement than male and female of B.Ed pupil teachers their external Locus of Control.

INTRODUCTION

Education in every human community is an indispensable instrument for human progress and empowerment. Any nation that lacks a sound educational culture and philosophy stands the risk of decay because education (primary, secondary and higher) plays a vital role in the overall development of a country. One of the major roles of educators is to develop in student's skills and knowledge that would make them function effectively in the society. Thus, students' academic performance is a major variable that interest both teachers and educational psychologists.

Education has become highly competitive and commercial in many countries.. The outcome of education determines the quality of life, progress and status of people living anywhere in the world (Mayuri & Devi, 2003). Academic performance is a complex behavior. Research has consistently shown that academic achievement is not an outcome of any single factor; rather it is the result of the interplay of a large number of factors (Gupta, 1993). Many reasons have been advanced as the cause of high rates of failure, including bad study habits, low IQ, faulty teaching methods, erroneous examination systems, social and economic disparities etc. The outcome of the study is expected to be helpful in developing effective intervention strategies aimed at improving student's performance and also in suggesting suitable changes in the governmental policies of education.

ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT

Academic achievement is the core of the entire educational growth. It is regarded as an important goal of education. Academic achievement is the outcome of the instruction provided to the children in schools which is determined by the grades, or marks secured by the students in the examination.

LOCUS OF CONTROL

Locus of control is an individual's belief regarding the causes of his or her experiences and the factors to which that person attributes success or failure (Njus & Brockway, 1999). This can either be internal or external (Rotter, 1966). If a person has an internal locus of control, that person attributes success to his or her own effort and abilities (Tella, 2009). A person who expects to succeed will be more motivated and more likely to learn. This person will seek out information and is more likely to have good study habits and a positive academic attitude. A person with an external locus of control on the other hand, will be less likely to make the effort to learn since he or she attributes his or her success to luck or fate. In relation to academic achievement, internal were more likely to believe that the achievement was related to their ability and failure related to a lack of effort (Thelma, 1998). to note that locus of control is a continuum. No one has a 100 percent external or internal locus of control. Instead, most people lie somewhere on the continuum between the two extremes.

Internal locus of control is often used synonymously with "self-determination" and "personal agency." Research has suggested that men tend to have a higher internal locus of control than women and that locus of control tends to become more internal as people grow older. Experts have found that, in general, people with an internal locus of control tend to be better off.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

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OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS OF THE TERMS USED

Academic Achievement: Academic achievement or academic performance is the outcome of education— the extent to which a student, teacher or institution has achieved their educational goals. In this study academic achievement refers to the score obtained at graduation level.

Locus of Control: Locus of control is a theory in personality psychology referring to the extent to which individuals believe that they can control events that affect them. A person's "locus" is conceptualized as either internal or external meaning they believe that their decisions and life are controlled by environmental factors which they cannot influence. In this study, locus of control refers to the score obtained by B.Ed. people teachers in the locus of control scale by Husnain and Joshi.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the relationship between academic achievement and locus of control of B.Ed. pupil teachers.
2. To compare the academic achievement of B.Ed. pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control.
3. To compare the academic achievement of B.Ed. male pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control.
4. To compare the academic achievement of B.Ed. female pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

1. There exists no significant relationship between academic achievement and locus of control of B.Ed. pupil teachers.
2. There exists no significant difference in academic achievement of B.Ed. pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control.
3. There exists no significant difference in academic achievement of B.Ed. male pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control.
4. There exists no significant difference in academic achievement of B.Ed. female pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control.

DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Keeping in view the time available and limited resources, the present study was delimited to the following aspects:-

- 1) The study was delimited to 120 B.Ed. pupil-teachers only.
- 2) The sample was taken from B.Ed colleges situated at Rohtak district only.
- 3) Only academic achievement was taken as dependent variable in the present study.
- 4) The study was delimited to find out the effect of independent variables locus of control .

TOOLS USED

1. Locus of Control Scale (LCS) By Hasnain and Joshi (1992)
2. Academic Achievements Scores have been taken from the B.Ed. pupil teachers from their graduation marks.

RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

Objective 1 : To study the relationship between academic achievement and locus of control of B.Ed. pupil teachers.

Hypothesis 1: There exists no significant relationship between academic achievement and locus of control of B.Ed. pupil teachers.

Table 4.1

Co-efficient of correlation between academic achievement and locus of control of B.Ed. pupil-teachers

Variables	N	Coefficient of correlation
Academic Achievement	120	-0.091 ^{NS}
External locus of control	120	
Academic Achievement	120	0.512 ^{**}
Internal locus of control	120	

NS = Not significant; **Significant at 0.01 level

The table 4.1 depicts that co-efficient of correlation between academic achievement and external locus of control of pupil teachers is -0.091 which is not significant at any level. It indicates that academic achievement and external locus of control of pupil teachers are not correlated with each other. It can be said that external type of locus of control has no influence on academic achievement of pupil teachers.

The next part of the table that co-efficient of correlation between academic achievement and internal locus of control of pupil teachers is 0.512 which is positively significant at 0.01 level. It indicates that academic achievement and external locus of control of pupil teachers has positive relationship with each other. Hence, the null hypothesis, "There exists no significant relationship between academic achievement and locus of control of B.Ed. pupil-teachers" is retained between academic achievement and external locus of control, while not retained between academic achievement and internal locus of control of pupil teachers.

Objective 2: To compare the academic achievement of B.Ed. pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control.

Hypothesis 2: There exists no significant difference in academic achievement of B.Ed. pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control.

Table 4.2

Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' values of academic achievement of B.Ed. pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control

	Number	Mean	S.D.	't'	Level of Significance
External locus of control	31	56.61	14.61	11.420	Significant at 0.01 level
Internal locus of control	74	82.06	14.83		

Fig. 4.1: Mean values of academic achievement of B.Ed. pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control

From table 4.2, it is clear that the mean score of academic achievement of B.Ed. pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control are 56.61 & 82.06 respectively. The calculated ‘t’ value for 103 degree of freedom is 11.420 which is more than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 and 2.58 at 0.01 level of significance. It means that there is a significant difference in academic achievement of B.Ed. pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control. Hence the null hypothesis, “There exists no significant difference in academic achievement of B.Ed. pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control” is not retained. The higher mean score of B.Ed. pupil-teachers having internal locus of control shows that they have better academic achievement than B.Ed. pupil-teachers having external locus of control.

Objective 3: To compare the academic achievement of B.Ed. male pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control.

Hypothesis 3: There exists no significant difference in academic achievement of B.Ed. male pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control.

Table 4.3

Mean, Standard Deviation and ‘t’ values of academic achievement of B.Ed. male pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control

	Number	Mean	S.D.	‘t’	Level of Significance
Male pupil teachers with external locus of control	12	57.71	8.63	11.756	Significant at 0.01 level
Male pupil teachers with internal locus of control	40	86.13	5.42		

Fig. 4.2: Mean values of academic achievement of female B.Ed. pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control

From table 4.3, it is clear that the mean score of academic achievement of male B.Ed. pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control are 56.37 & 79.66 respectively. The calculated 't' value for 43 degree of freedom is 8.774 which is more than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 and 2.58 at 0.01 level of significance. It means that there is a significant difference in academic achievement of male B.Ed. pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control. Hence the null hypothesis, "There exists no significant difference in academic achievement of male B.Ed. pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control" is not retained. The higher mean score of male B.Ed. pupil-teachers having internal locus of control shows that they have better academic achievement than male B.Ed. pupil-teachers having external locus of control.

Objective 4: To compare the academic achievement of B.Ed. female pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control.

Hypothesis 4: There exists no significant difference in academic achievement of B.Ed. female pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control.

Table 4.4

Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' values of academic achievement of B.Ed. female pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control

	Number	Mean	S.D.	't'	Level of Significance
Female pupil teachers with external locus of control	12	57.71	8.63	11.756	Significant at 0.01 level
Female pupil teachers with internal locus of control	40	86.13	5.42		

Fig. 4.3: Mean values of academic achievement of female B.Ed. pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control

From table 4.4., it is clear that the mean score of academic achievement of female B.Ed. pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control are 57.71 & 81.13 respectively. The calculated 't' value for 50 degree of freedom is 11.756 which is more than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 and 2.58 at 0.01 level of significance. It means that there is a significant difference in academic achievement of female B.Ed. pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control. Hence the null hypothesis, "There exists no significant difference in academic achievement of B.Ed. female pupil-teachers having internal and external locus of control" is not retained. The higher mean score of male B.Ed. pupil-teachers having internal locus of control shows that they have better academic achievement than female B.Ed. pupil-teachers having external locus of control.

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